

LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF ADVERTISING TEXTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. The article researched the linguistic aspects found in Uzbek language advertising texts. As the advertising industry is developing daily, the progress of many industries remains dependent on the advertising factor. This requires the use of linguistic styles, a language that is prominent and attracts attention in advertising texts. This paper explored the phonetically, lexically, and syntactically of advertising texts in Uzbek and English, which have been applied in various fields. Rhythmic words were identified, giving examples of the phonological tool of rhyme regarding the phonetic level. The linguistic method and sentence structure, which refers to the lexical and syntactic levels of the language, has been thoroughly studied on a scientific basis.

Keywords: advertising, linguistic style, linguistic medium, phonetic, lexical, syntactic

INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA REKLAMA MATNLARINING LINGVISTIK TAHLILI

Annotatsiya. Maqolada o'zbek tilidagi reklama matnlarida uchraydigan lingvistik jihatlar tadqiq qilindi. Reklama sanoati kundan-kunga rivojlanib borayotganligi sababli ko'plab sohalarning taraqqiy etishi reklama omiliga bog'liq bo'lib qolmoqda. Bu esa reklama matnlarida ko'zga tashlanadigan va e'tiborni

jalb qiladigan tildan ya'ni lingvistik uslublardan foydalanishni talab qilmoqda. Ushbu maqolada turli sohalarda qo'llanilgan o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi reklama matnlari fonetik, leksik va sintaktik jihatdan o'rganildi. Fonetik sathga oid qofiya fonologik vositasiga misollar berilib ritmik so'zlar aniqlandi. Tilning leksik va sintaktik sathlariga oid bo'lgan lingvistik usul va gap tuzilishi ilmiy asosda sinchiklab o'rganildi.

Kalit so'zlar: reklama, lingvistik uslub, lingvistik vosita, fonetik, leksik, sintaktik

ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ АНАЛИЗ РЕКЛАМНЫХ ТЕКСТОВ АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. В статье были исследованы лингвистические аспекты, встречающиеся в рекламных текстах на узбекском языке. Поскольку рекламная индустрия развивается день ото дня, прогресс многих отраслей остается в зависимости от рекламного фактора. Это требует использования языка, то есть лингвистических стилей, которые выделяются и привлекают внимание в рекламных текстах. В данной статье были изучены фонетически, лексически и синтаксически рекламные тексты на узбекском и английском языках, применяемые в различных областях. Приведены примеры фонологического средства рифмовки относительно фонетического уровня и определены ритмические слова. Лингвистический метод и структура предложения, относящиеся к лексическому и синтаксическому уровням языка, были тщательно изучены на научной основе.

Ключевые слова: реклама, лингвистический стиль, лингвистический инструмент, фонетический, лексический, синтаксический

Introduction: Advertising is getting deeper into our life day by day and becoming an integral part of it. Today, wherever we look, our eyes are

It's not a mistake to say that it comes down to advertising: billboards, photos of clothes and vehicles, online ads, radio and TV ads... This situation requires organizations and companies that want to sell their services or products to use effective methods of advertising. According to Mohammad Shariq [Mohammad Shariq, 2020, p.565], "Today's

In the advanced age, the main goal of advertising creators is not to reach more people, but to reach people's minds and stay there for a long time. The only way to achieve this goal is to pay attention to the advertising language and make effective use of linguistic tools. In his article, Balaji Natkare [2012] listed five objectives of advertising: to attract attention, arouse interest, create desire, persuade, and induce purchase. Below is information about the definitions of linguistic methods and tools used to achieve these goals and their use in advertising texts.

Literature review and methodology

First, let's talk about the origin of the word "advertising". From the middle of the 19th century, the role of advertising in the economy increased dramatically, and it spread mainly through newspapers and magazines. Since the 20th century, television, radio, Internet, and mail advertising began [wikipedia, 2023].

Many scientists have researched advertising language and studied it linguistically. For example, Leech [1972, p27] defined the main principles of advertising text: Attention value, Readability, Memorability and Selling power.

With the change of times, the requirements for the advertising text also change, which requires constant awareness of the latest scientific innovations in this field. Including, in recent years, a lot of scientific work on advertising text has been carried out. These studies examined various aspects of advertising text, including impact, readability, effectiveness, and persuasive language. Motes et al. (1992), Myers (1997), Foster (2001), Ding (2003), Kohli et al. (2007), Christopher (2012), and Fatihi (2014), many scholars have made a significant

contribution to the field of studying advertising language and its linguistic aspects. They analysed various aspects of advertising text and stimulated developments in this field. However, contributions in this field have not lost their importance, and the reason for this is the growing role of the advertising industry.

In this article, the methods of comparative analysis, deduction, and linguistic description (observation, interpretation, comparison, generalization, and classification) were used to study the linguistic aspects of advertising texts in English and Uzbek languages.

Discussion and results

Phonetic level

The term phonetics is derived from the Greek word "phonetikos" meaning "pertaining to sound, sonorous, voiced", and refers to the methods of formation and acoustic properties of speech sounds in linguistics; syllable, a part of speech that is separated by a pause. From the point of view of the phonetic level, the peculiarities created by the sounds in the advertising texts are studied. In the phonetic part of the study, examples of the rhyming method were given from the linguistic tools used in the advertising text.

Rhyme

Rhyme is a phonetic melodious tool widely used in poetry and advertising texts, and it is achieved by repeating the same sounds. According to Leech [1972], rhyme makes advertising texts easier to remember. Below are examples of ads that use rhyme to create a tone.

Advertising text	rhythm-generated words
Bu Roll Ball saqich, bu esa Ketti Ooo Shirin bo'p ketti	Ketti – ketti
Har lahza Pepsi bilan mazza!	Lahza – mazza

A'lo ta'm Candy Goldda mujassam!	Ta'm – mujassam
Og'riq kelsa bu demak – Yordamchi Atsafenak	Demak – Atsafenak
Alyumag – oshqozonga ko'mak	Alyumag – ko'mak

Advertising text	rhythm-generated words
Late night Great night Turn left at Light	Night – Light
Beauty outside. Beast inside.	Outside – Inside
Grace. Space. Pace.	Grace – Space – Pace
Oh thank heaven for 7-Eleven	Heaven – Eleven
Pepsi-Cola hits the spot Twelve full ounces, that's a lot.	Spot – a lot

Lexical level

The lexical level of linguistics is related to the vocabulary of the language and deals with the use of homonyms or compound words, neologisms, pronouns, adjectives or idioms. The words used in the advertising text are one of the main factors in its effectiveness. For this reason, it is necessary to choose words carefully. During the research of advertising texts in Uzbek and English languages, the features related to the use of words were studied, and you can get acquainted with the results of the analysis of the use of words in the table below.

Advertising text	Application of adjectives
Quvnoq ta'm Sladokda mujassam! Mifon – og'ir ovqat uchun yengil yechim Lactovita – ona tabiatning shifobaxsh	Quvnoq, yengil, shifobaxsh, barakali, mazali, sof, tabiiy.

siri! Artel – barakali texnika Hot lunch – ta'mi o'zgacha mazali! Nestle – mutlaqo sof va tabiiy	
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Advertising text	Application of adjectives
Life is complicated Breakfast should be simple Who knew delicious could be so nutritious? Warm cookies and Free hugs Small price. Big cheese-eating grin. Hard Breakfast? Soft Breakfast? No Breakfast?	Complicated, simple, delicious, nutritious, warm, free, small, big, hard, soft

According to Yanping Fan [2013], adjectives used in advertising texts can be divided into two groups: descriptive adjectives and evaluative adjectives.

Examples of descriptive adjectives are healing, blessed, and natural. The evaluative adjectives include the words cheerful and light. The use of adjectives is the most effective way to increase the effectiveness of advertising. As stated by Leech [1966], the language of advertising is judged by the excessive use of adjectives.

Advertising text	Application of adverbs
Candy Gold – har kungi quvonch! Artel – doimo birga! Artel– har kun yanada yaxshiroq!	Har kungi, doimo, har kun, yanada, har tong, kun-u tun, rohatda, hotirjam.

Shvetskoe – har tong siz bilan! Kun-u tun, shirintoyingiz uchun – Perla Perla – bolalar – rohatda, onalar – hotirjam!	
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Advertising text	Application of adverbs
Get your dream car quickly and easily with our financing options Experience the world’s finest luxury vacation exclusively with our resort You can’t run from us forever	Quickly, easily, exclusively, forever

Advertising text	Application of interrogative sentences
Kango qani? Hey! Sendachi Zizi bormi? Uyingizga sifatli mebellar kerakmi? Poytaxt mebel Tanaffusmi? Kit-kat bor	Qani, bormi, kerakmi, tanaffusmi

Advertising text	Application of interrogative sentences
How could two coffees transform your business? The ugly carrot in a soup who cares? Have you driven a Ford lately? Do you Yahoo?	How, Who, Have you, Do you, Is it

Is it live, or is it Memorex?	
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Advertising text	Application of personality pronouns
Hey! Sendachi Zizi bormi? 7 Утра – kun sendan boshlanadi Septolete – sening tomog'ing – sening Kuching Hayot sifati sizning likopchangizdan boshlanadi	Sendachi, sendan, sening, sizning

Advertising text	Application of personality pronouns
I'm lovin' it. Because you're worth it Love. It's what makes a Subaru Belong anywhere It's our pleasure to serve you!	I, it, you, anywhere, our

By using personal pronouns, it is possible to reduce the distance between the manufacturer and the customer, as if the manufacturer is speaking face-to-face with the customer and giving his sincere recommendation through advertising [Hangrong, 2003].

Syntactic level

The syntactic level is a branch of linguistics that studies the rules of linking words and making sentences to form a sentence.

Syntactically, sentences can be divided into four groups: declarative, interrogative, command and exclamatory sentences. From a syntactic point of view, the main goal of the structure of the advertising text is to attract the consumer's attention and arouse interest in it.

Type of the sentence	Advertising text
Declarative sentence	Eng yaxshi kayfiyat Chocotella bilan boshlanar.
Interrogative sentence	Uyingizga sifatli mebellar kerakmi? Poytaxt mebel
Imperative sentence	Hayotni butun jigaringiz bilan seving!
Exclamatory sentence	Cheers – tandirdan uzilgan chipslar!

Type of the sentence	Advertising text
Declarative sentence	Mary had a little lamb, fries and a Coke
Interrogative sentence	How could two coffees transform your business?
Imperative sentence	Give a happy ending to your meal!
Exclamatory sentence	It's our pleasure to serve you!

This analysis was done from a general perspective. However, if the specific features of advertising texts are taken into account after thorough analysis, it will be possible to add other categories such as simple sentences or incomplete sentences to the list. Thus, the success of advertising slogans depends not only on correctly chosen words but also on the syntactic structure of the text.

The syntactically short and concise text makes it easy to understand and remember [Elena N. Malyuga & Barry Tomalin, 2020].

Conclusion

Based on the scientific-practical materials and results analyzed in the article, it can be concluded that the use of various linguistic tools in advertising texts in English and Uzbek is growing significantly compared to previous years, and the main goal of advertising texts is to make people's minds faster. and easy

to install. Because the development of many industries depends on the advertising industry, which has led to increased attention to the advertising text. When the advertising text was analyzed from the phonetic level, it was found that the rhyming tool is widely used in the advertising texts in both languages, and it was found that it serves to make the advertising text memorable by creating melody. The analysis of the lexical level showed that when creating advertising texts in English and Uzbek, attention is mainly paid to the use of words that evoke a positive mood. As for the syntactic level analysis, not only the choice of words, and tone but also the structure of the sentence play an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the advertising text. Because the structure of the sentence is a linguistic tool that can attract the attention of the consumer and is an important factor that must be taken into account.

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